

The Impact of Early Experiences in Childhood in *Wuthering Heights* and *The God of Small Things*

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Abstract

Max Muller states that "all higher knowledge is gained by comparison and rests on comparison" (Dhawan, 1987). T.S. Eliot also states in his *Tradition and Individual Talent* that an artist is important only when he is compared and contrasted with other artists. Comparison of two different authors from two different cultures, countries and different periods resulted in a deeper understanding of the works and their authors. This paper is an attempt to explore the fictional world of two women writers separated by time, place, and culture. *Wuthering Heights* by Emily Brontë and *The God of Small Things* by Arundhati Roy are taken for this paper.

Wuthering Heights was published in 1847 under the pseudonym 'Ellis Bell'. This novel smote the London society and produced strong and hostile criticism. A year later, Emily Brontë passed away in 1848 as a victim of the family disease. Suzanna Arundhati Roy was born in 1960 in Shillong to a Bengali Hindu family as the second child of Rajib Roy and Mary Issac from Kerala. After the divorce, Mary Roy returned to Kerala with her two children. The aristocratic and conservative Mary's family declined to accept her and her children since she had married and divorced, leaving behind the family's conventions and wishes. Roy was a toddler when her parents got divorced. The fusion of different cultures has shaped and influenced their perceptions and outlook for both Roy and Brontë. Both fictions are basically a love story. These novels also deal with the childhood of almost all the characters.

Key Words: Early Experiences, Long for Love and Affection, Displacement, Separation, Verbal, Physical, and Sexual Abuse, Victims of Injustice and Stunted Growth of Childhood.

Max Muller states that “all higher knowledge is gained by comparison and rests on comparison” (Dhawan, 1987). T.S. Eliot also states in his *Tradition and Individual Talent* that an artist is important only when he is compared and contrasted with other artists. Comparison of two different authors from two different cultures, countries and different periods resulted in a deeper understanding of the works and their authors. This paper is an attempt to explore the fictional world of two women writers separated by time, place, and culture. *Wuthering Heights* by Emily Brontë and *The God of Small Things* by Arundhati Roy are taken for this paper.

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Richard Chase claims that childhood is the central theme of Brontë’s writings. The story concerns the childhood of the main characters, Heathcliff, Catherine, Isabella, Hindley Earnshaw, Cathy and Linton. The importance of childhood in shaping characters could be seen in *Wuthering Heights*. Brontë renders exclusive importance to heredity and child characters and their traits. Even grown-ups are seen as adults arrested in childhood. Brontë’s novels are a replica of childhood joys and sorrows, and the focus is on the burden of childhood that is growing up without the love and care of parents, which manifests in stunted growth and prevents them from attaining normal emotional growth.

The experience of Childhood days made an indelible mark on every individual. The emotional violence in the novel resulted in childhood trauma and neglect. Brontë refers to Heathcliff: “he exemplifies the effects which a life of continued injustice and hard usage may produce... tyranny and ignorance made him a mere demon” (Allot,56). All kids suffer, those loved and unloved, in many ways. This novel explores the early experiences of the two generations through Nelly’s point of view.

The theme of childhood is voiced by Catherine, “I wish I were a girl again”, exclaims the dying Catherine (91). Childhood is the period in the life of most individuals when they feel close to their origin and experience a transient vision of innocence and happiness. For both Catherine and Heathcliff, maturity is synonymous with imprisonment, torment and loss. In the first part of the novel, Brontë portrays the childhood of the first Generation- Heathcliff, Catherine, Hindley, and Nelly as children. Catherine always allies with Heathcliff in their common rebellion against Hindley’s persecution. Heathcliff, ‘the dirty, ragged, starving, homeless black-haired orphan’ was picked up from the streets of Liverpool and brought to the Heights by Mr Earnshaw when Hindley was fourteen and Catherine was six. The immediate reaction from the family is hostility towards Heathcliff. Nelly refers to the child as ‘it’, therefore denying the child the human status. Consequently, he was treated with indifference and cruelty.

Heathcliff is depicted as the recipient of violence. His childhood is a pattern of victimisation, violence and injustice. He was blamed as a usurper of his father's affection and his privilege. Subsequently, it resulted in Hindley abusing him by calling him a 'dog', 'a gipsy', 'a beggarly interloper' and 'a imp of satan' (27). Only Catherine treated him as her equal. Hindley's reaction to show his hatred humiliates and degrades, and disintegrates Heathcliff from others. The seed of revenge against Heathcliff is shown in his mind.

Catherine, as a child, presented brimming with life and energy, and Heathcliff is really attached to her and is ready to do anything for her. In the patriarchal family, she shares Heathcliff's subordinate position after her father's death. As children, one of their chief amusements is to run away from the house to roam on the moors. When life becomes miserable and unbearable, the only resort for the kids is this moor. The affinity between Catherine and Heathcliff begins as a childhood togetherness, which later develops into a strange bond of oneness. Hence, Catherine admits that "He is myself than I am" (57). The greatest punishment for her is the separation from Heathcliff.

Naming a child is an emotional and sensitive one. Heathcliff, a boy adopted by Mr. Earnshaw, has no name at all. He is referred to with the impersonal pronoun 'it'. He was given the name Heathcliff, but there is no surname for him, which nullifies his presence in the genealogy of Mr. Earnshaw. Heathcliff suffers from the loss of identity and the loss of self. Catherine, as a female, she too senses the powerless in the patriarchal society and sometimes she experiences humiliation. The reason for marrying Edgar is that she can help Heathcliff rise from the bondage of Hindley. She states the reason as such: "If I marry Linton, I can aid Heathcliff to rise, and place him out of my brother's power" (58).

Catherine, as an adult, claims that "I was a child; my father was just buried, and my misery arose from the separation that Hindley ordered between me and Heathcliff. I was laid alone, for the first time" (91). Separation is unbearable for both Catherine and Heathcliff. The traumatic experience affects them greatly and distorts their life. Heathcliff was first abandoned by his parents, and he was betrayed by Catherine when she agreed to marry Edgar. The death of Mr Earnshaw, the change and the displacement hinder the bond between them. Both express their view that heaven is a miserable place when compared to their childhood days together. This traumatic destruction of childhood paradise results in the division of the self. Heathcliff and Catherine underwent the agonies of a divided self, and they sought moments and chances to bind together, but they failed due to the fiery and egoistic nature of Heathcliff.

In the first half of the novel, the main characters, Catherine, Heathcliff, Hindley, Edgar and Isabella represent the innocent childhood. Even after they grew up into adults, they behave and talk like children. They desire to retaliate for a slight indifference, negligence, insults and humiliation. They are too mature to mature emotionally. Everyone exhibits bits of affection, taunts, threats, and physical assaults, too. The reason is that most of them lost their mother's love and care, and this loss never repaired and cannot be healed. Their voices reflect the terror of a motherless child and the need for parental care.

As psychologist Nancy Verrier writes in *The Primal Wound: Understanding the Adopted Child*, in the article *Psychology Today* states that Boys who lost their mother at an early age could experience disrupted attachment and are vulnerable to separation anxiety, fears of abandonment, and difficulty with cognitive functions. Later in life, motherless sons may have difficulty with intimacy, especially with women. This can be applied to adopted boys and thus separated from their biological mothers.

Fairy tales continue to fascinate young minds from time immemorial, which influence the development and identity of the kids. There are many fairy tales of motherless daughters and motherless sons, who are often left in the clutches of evil stepmothers, as in *Snow White* and *Cinderella*. Charles Dickens had a special affection for his orphaned boys. Oliver Twist, David Copperfield, and Pip in *Great Expectations* had been abandoned by one or both parents. All three of these characters find maternal love and care in sympathetic women: Pip in Mrs. Joe and Oliver in Nancy. Huckleberry Finn and Peter Pan have rejected the rules of society and survive through their cleverness and wits. The seven dwarfs in the fairy tale *Snow White* are another type of lost boys, living in the woods outside the bounds of civilisation. They agree to let Snow White stay with them if she does the housekeeping, mends their clothes, and prepares their food—in short, becomes a mother substitute. They find their mother substitutes, which help them face the trials and difficulties, and they struggle and are forced to rise above their levels of abandonment.

These stories are told from generation to generation and they reflect the glimpses of something about ourselves, our secret wishes, fears and desires hidden from conscious awareness. As children, the terror of being abandoned by a mother or both parents is too frightening but even in our postmodern era, we recognize the anguish of fictional motherless sons. But they have an ability to survive, often by finding a mother substitute.

In reality, the loss of a mother or the lack of maternal care greatly affects all children. The loss or the separation may be the result of a death, divorce, or emotional abandonment; children need their loss acknowledged and addressed. They need guidance and support in handling their grief and help in being made to feel secure again after this abandonment.

Often, boys who are raised without a mother or maternal care may struggle with social skills. Without a maternally caring role model, boys have difficulty developing empathy and a capacity to nurture. They may adhere to traditionally strict gender roles, which could be observed in the behaviour of Heathcliff.

Wuthering Heights could be compared with Roy's *The God of Small Things* through the lens of childhood. Childhood is figured not through images but by the words and phrases that are repeated and recur in the novel as images. Raji Narasimhan comments that *The God of Small Things* presents the psychological scars of childhood. Roy explicates in an emotive way what it means to be a child who comes from a broken or dysfunctional family. The story is about children who are abandoned and neglected by adults, their traumatic childhood experiences, who suffer from a lack of love, their stunted emotional development and lead to abnormal behaviours.

Estha stops speaking when he is molested at the age of seven by the Lemondrink Man. Estha's mind grows more melancholy. The narrator states this event as "these are only the small things". Throughout the formative years, both have been subjected to psychological trauma that leaves persistent fear and anxiety in their lives. Both Rahel and her twin brother Estha are deeply scarred by the betrayals they face from their family. Rahel, in an attempt to feel close to someone, commits incest with her brother in a crescendo of horror and grief at the end of the novel. Estha's separation from his mother and his twin sister, the child's sexual abuse, and the betrayal of the loved person are catalysts that leave their imprint on the lives of the twins.

Arundhati Roy's "The God of Small Things" vividly portrays the stark contrast between the innocence of childhood and the harsh realities that the young protagonists encounter. The twins Estha and Rahel pass through the tumultuous childhood spoiled by parental strife, familial negligence, selfish and uncaring adults. The kids constantly live in the fear of being less loved and unloved.

The world of the children is filled with imagination, inventiveness, incomplete understanding, fears, dependence, and assertion of independence, vulnerability, comradeship, jealousy, and wonderment are beautifully knitted in the story. Roy depicts the small enjoyments and wonders of childhood of the twins through two symbols- the river Meenachi and the boat. The activities in the river- discovering the 'vallom' and that takes them to the 'akkare' where their harmless play acting, word play, their dressing up in sarees, singing folk songs, swimming, fishing and playing in the river shower happiness in their loveless parched land.

The perspective of children offers a unique lens which explores how childhood experiences shape adult lives and how early they encounter trauma, abuse, and injustice, which leave an indelible mark on their development. In their early life, the twins are exposed to cruelty, violence, domestic abuse and caste discrimination, which erodes their innocence. Estha's molestation forces him to be silent and detached. They witness the brutality of the beastly beatings of the police and the death of Velutha at the hands of the police. Furthermore, both witness and behave unjustly when they are pressured to betray Velutha.

The twins became the victims of adult failures, such as their unfulfilled desires, Kochamma's manipulative nature, and Ammu's striving for individuality. All contribute to the kids' misery. Consequently, they feel unprotected. The title focuses on 'small things', seemingly insignificant moments, details that collectively accumulate, shape and impact the children's lives largely.

Both kids long for emotional attachment and solace, which are denied to them persistently. Both are treated with utmost hatred as unwelcome creatures by their grandma. They don't even have home live together but are separated. Roy's non-linear narrative projects the disturbed, distressed and desperate minds of the twins. Both have suffered due to the physical and psychological negligence and rejection.

Roy skillfully weaves a tale that projects how events during formative years can impact relationships, family dynamics, and personal growth well into adulthood. By portraying these experiences of children, Roy effectively emphasises the significance of small things in shaping their lives' trajectory. In conclusion, Roy emphasises through *The God of Small Things* how these early experiences, the traumas and societal prejudices are imprinted upon young minds, whether small or great, unnoticed by adults, profoundly shape the adult self, leaving an indelible scar of sorrow and alienation.

Both novelists, Roy and Bronte, make it a point through these novels that childhood experiences play a prominent part in shaping the character and the behaviour of the person when he or she grows as an adult. Estha and Rahel cannot see them as separate individuals, just like Heathcliff and Catherine in *Wuthering Heights*. Separation brings chaos into their life. Heathcliff and Catherine find their refuge in running away from the house to roam on the moors. When life becomes miserable and unbearable, the only resort for the kids is this moor. In *The God of Small Things*, the river and the boat provide them the joy and amusement for the twins Estha and Rahel.

These two novels share a lot of similarities in themes and style. Betrayal of the loved one is a common theme in both novels. Catherine betrays Heathcliff when she agrees to marry Edgar. Similarly, Estha is forced to betray Velutha to save his mother. Both novels are dominated by pain, suffering, separation, loss of love, longing for love, and desertion. These indelible scars harm innocent lives. Both could be seen as 'Bildungsroman since they deal with the growth and development of characters from their childhood to adulthood. Both novels depict the rebellious nature of children as born out of neglect and a lack of love. They emphasise the importance of mother – child in the development of the child since attachment and loss have profound importance in human development. In both novels, those in power fear the heroes, Heathcliff and Velutha. Significantly, these novels deal with the consequences of violence against children, especially of child abuse. They reflect on how it affects the psyche of children who become victims of physical and sexual abuse. The concept of violence, terror, suffering and intolerance can be seen in both novels. Heathcliff and Catherine represent the two fictionalised selves of Emily Brontë, just like Estha and Rahel in *The God of Small Things* are fictionalised selves of Arundhati Roy. Both novels have love and childhood as themes. In *Wuthering Heights*, the focus is on the childhood of Heathcliff and Catherine, whereas in *The God of Small Things*, the focus is on Estha and Rahel, not on Ammu and Velutha. Both novels are preeminently by women, about women and seen through the eyes of women. But it deals with childhood in the choice of words and the vocabulary.

To conclude, both novels picture the unheard voices of childhood and all the characters exhibit a tidbit of affection, threats, physical, sexual and verbal abuse. The loss of motherly love and care stunt their development and the ailments and the pain of the separation crave for care and love never be healed. It wounded their psyche. But in *Wuthering Heights*, it is compensated by the foster-mother, Nelly.

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